

Mechanistic Aspects of the Selectivity of RuO₂ and Ru–Mn–O Catalysts in Parallel Chlorine and Oxygen Evolutions Reactions

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ABSTRACT: Mechanistic differences between oxygen evolution and chlorine evolution on Ru-based oxide electrodes in acidic media were assessed by in situ soft X-ray absorption spectroscopy. O K-edge spectra recorded under cyclic polarization in 0.1 M HClO₄ containing variable concentrations of chlorides in energy dispersion mode were used to follow the potential dependence of the key intermediates in the oxygen evolution process as a function of the electrode potential and chloride concentration. In the absence of chlorides, the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) process is characterized by the formation of surface-confined OOH at potentials preceding the onset of the bulk oxygen evolution. In the presence of chlorides, the spectral behavior reflects a change of the electrode selectivity towards chlorine evolution, which shows a suppression of the absorption of the gaseous oxygen as well as intermediates of the OER process. The observed behavior is compliant with a mechanism assuming chlorine binding via surface-confined oxygen atoms. The Ru–Mn–O phases, which are selective for oxygen evolution even in the presence of chlorides, show a different behavior. The sites involved in the OER retain their selectivity to the OER even in the presence of chlorides. The actual mechanism of the OER changes in the presence of chlorides. While in the absence of chlorides one observes accumulation of surface OOH groups only at potentials positive to the onset of the bulk oxygen evolution, the presence of chlorides enables the formation of surface-confined OOH at potentials negative to the onset of the OER. The onset of the actual oxygen evolution, on the other hand, leads to removal of the surface-confined OOH, suggesting that the OER is controlled by the third electron transfer in the presence of chlorides.

KEYWORDS: ruthenium dioxide, oxygen evolution, chlorine evolution, soft X-ray absorption spectroscopy, reaction mechanism

INTRODUCTION

Hydrogen production for renewable energy storage has increased interest in electrocatalytic gas-evolving reactions, as water electrolysis represents the most promising process for environmentally acceptable production of hydrogen. In fact, water electrolysis as a process is not actually controlled by cathodic hydrogen evolution but by kinetically sluggish oxygen evolution, which represents the main limiting factor for a large-scale deployment of water electrolyzers.¹ It also needs to be added that the large-scale utilization of electrolytic hydrogen generation can face a problem with availability and purity of fresh water for water electrolysis, namely due to a need to avoid the presence of chlorides. Alternative solutions include desalination of sea water or, ultimately, sea water electrolysis,^{2–5} in which one needs to tackle a parallel anodic chlorine evolution.

Anodically generated chlorine represents an unwanted byproduct of the electrolysis of chloride-containing water due to its toxicity and corrosiveness. Selectivity control of the parallel anodic gas evolution reactions represents a fundamental issue which can be addressed via exploring the different pH

dependence of the two processes^{4,6,7} and/or by controlling the intrinsic selectivity of the catalyst's surface. Resulting from different pH dependence of chlorine and oxygen evolution reactions, the thermodynamic preference of the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) (at a constant potential) increases with increasing pH. An alternative approach toward selectivity control can be associated with engineering the surface to control the nature and abundance of the active sites supporting the corresponding electrode reaction(s).^{5,8–11} Doing so may steer the selectivity of the oxide catalyst's surface in these gas-evolving reactions. One needs to stress the fact that a detailed understanding of both electrode processes and their mechanisms is a prerequisite to rational design of novel selective electrode materials.¹² Despite the undisputable success of

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experiments to prepare novel catalytically active systems with controlled selectivity,^{5,9–14} there are practically no experimental reports which would pin down the actual mechanisms of both gas-evolving reactions at electrode surfaces. The anodic gas evolution on oxide-based surfaces has been treated theoretically.^{8,15–18} This theoretical analysis was based on practical application of Brønsted–Polanyi relations, which allow assessment of thermodynamic limits of kinetic behavior by comparing the driving forces of given reactions at different electrode surfaces. Such DFT-based thermodynamic analysis clearly points toward a kinetic preference of chlorine evolution for most of the conceivable surfaces.⁸ Chlorine as well as oxygen evolution in relevant pH ranges proceed under rather harsh conditions, which explains the disproportionate attention paid to the behavior of electrode materials based on noble metal oxides (mostly on Ru and Ir) and their solid solutions with, e.g., Ti.^{19–23}

Regarding the practical steering of the selectivity in parallel oxygen and chlorine evolution, it was shown that the preference for a particular gas-evolving reaction can be altered by controlling the surface stress and strain of the catalytically active layer.²⁴ The selectivity of the Ru-based catalysts is also affected by chemical composition and/or by the local structure, as has been shown for ternary systems of the Ru–Me–O (Me = Ni, Mn, Zn, Mg) type.^{5,9,11,12} A similar local structure effect has also been reported for well-defined single-phase catalysts in the Ru–Ti–O system.²³ In a similar manner, the behavior of Ir-based systems, despite their less favorable cost, was examined in detail for Ir-based double perovskites²⁴ or for phases in the Ir–Mn–O system.¹⁹ It should be noted, that the results of these studies still need to be corroborated theoretically.

In the light of the prospective use of novel catalysts in hydrogen-producing electrolysis of chloride-containing solutions, one needs to pay particular attention to the several systems which have been reported to steer the selectivity of the surface toward oxygen evolution even in the presence of significant chloride content.^{5,12,14,24} Using ruthenium-based oxides related to dimensional stable anodes (DSAs) as model materials, one needs to stress that a substitution with Zn⁵ or Mn^{12,14} yields materials with a particular tendency to evolve the oxygen from chloride-containing media. In this light, these systems significantly differ from those substituted by Ni¹¹ or Mg,⁹ which show a high preference for chlorine evolution.

The generalized computational models of the oxygen and chlorine evolution on Ru-oxide-based surfaces predict a competition between the two electrode reactions for the surface-active sites for all involved surfaces. The proposed active site competition has, however, never been proved experimentally.⁶ The lack of experimental evidence regarding the nature of the active sites and/or of the reaction mechanism can be, in part, connected with the experimental difficulty in addressing the actual surface structure under operando conditions of oxygen and/or chlorine evolution. This situation has changed recently with the advent of operando soft X-ray spectroscopic techniques.^{25,26} While hard X-ray-based spectroscopic techniques have been explored for several decades due to their compatibility with the conditions of the anodic gas-evolving reactions, their actual impact on the understanding of these processes was rather limited due to the bulk nature of X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS). Using soft X-rays in part mends the surface sensitivity issue since the fluorescence registered in soft X-ray absorption spectroscopy originates in

relatively thin surface layer thickness of less than 100 nm. In fact, operando soft X-ray techniques (both XPS²⁵ and XAS^{26–29}) have been employed to address the behavior of some Ru- and Ir-based catalysts in the OER.

Given the interdependence of both anodic gas-evolving reactions at oxide-based electrode surfaces, one may use O K-edge soft XAS to characterize the selectivity control of the anode surface in parallel with the OER and chlorine evolution reaction (CER). The OER is conventionally described as a sequence of four consecutive one-electron, one-proton steps, as outlined in the sequence of reactions (1)–(4):

Aside from the DFT-based investigations, the OER reaction mechanism has been also followed experimentally using the soft X-ray-based technique, which proved to be instrumental in following the surface population of theoretically conceived reaction intermediates—namely those formed in the reactions (1) and (2).^{25–30} Aside from the qualitative and quantitative determination of the surface-confined oxygen-containing species acting as OER intermediates, soft X-ray absorption spectroscopy reflects the development of the local electronic structure near the transition metal. The energy-dispersive operando O K-edge XAS data clearly show that the bulk oxygen evolution leads to a change in the local electronic structure under the OER conditions. This change in the electronic structure shows itself in suppression probability of the excitation of the O 1s electrons into unoccupied bands formed by a hybridization of O 2p* orbitals with Ru 4d e_g orbitals.²⁹

The chlorine evolution process, on the other hand, includes a transfer of only two electrons and can be summarized by two conceivable reaction sequences, summarized by equations (5)–(7) and (8)–(9):

It needs to be noted that, while the reaction sequence (5)–(7) represents a catalytic cycle formally independent of the oxygen evolution, the reaction sequence represented by processes (8)–(9) relies on the same active sites as the catalytic cycle of the OER and suggests strong competition between the two electrode processes. At the same time, it clearly identifies O K-edge XAS as a convenient tool to follow the actual drivers controlling the selectivity of the oxide surfaces in parallel oxygen and chlorine evolution.

This paper extends the previous studies in which O K-edge XAS was employed to follow the oxygen evolution process on Ru oxide-based surfaces. We compare the data obtained by energy-dispersed XAS to elucidate the chemical changes governing the selectivity behavior of various Ru-based oxides. Specifically, we compare here the behavior of pure RuO₂,

which is known to be rather selective for CER, with that of $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$, which has been reported to retain high oxygen-evolving selectivity,^{12,14} even in the presence of significant chloride concentrations.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

XAS Experiments. The soft X-ray absorption spectra of nanoparticulate Ru and Ru–Mn oxides were measured at beamline BL-16A at the Photon Factory under high-vacuum conditions. The XAS spectra were measured in a conventional stepwise manner in the energy range 510–670 eV. The individual step size was 1 eV, with an integration time of 3 s. The absorption spectra were recorded in partial fluorescence mode with a single-element silicon drift detector (SDD) (SGX Sensortech) used as the fluorescence detector.

Real-time *in situ* XAS measurements on the O K-edge were performed in total fluorescence-yield mode using the wavelength-dispersive XAS approach.³¹ All the experiments were performed at beamline BL-16A of the Photon Factory of the High Energy Accelerator Research Organization (KEK), Japan.³¹ Figure 1 shows a schematic image of the apparatus

Figure 1. (a) Schematic representation of the apparatus for energy-dispersive XAS on the O K-edge and (b) a dedicated electrochemical cell.

configuration. The electrochemical cell filled with liquid electrolyte solution (0.1 M HClO_4) was separated from the high-vacuum part of the XAS apparatus (beamline and imaging optics) by a Si_3N_4 window (NTT-AT Japan), which was fabricated on a Si wafer with a thickness of 200 nm and dimensions of 1 mm \times 3 mm.

The spatial dispersion of the synchrotron radiation at the exit slit of the soft X-ray monochromator²⁶ was achieved with a 500 lines/mm diffraction grating optimized to provide soft X-rays around the O K-edge (approximately 530 eV). Incoming X-rays on the grating are diffracted according to their wavelength at distinctive angles, and as a result, individual wavelengths hit different positions at the sample. Fluorescence signals proportional to the absorption of incident soft X-rays were recorded simultaneously using a metal oxide semiconductor (CMOS) camera (Marana-X, Andor) as a detector

(pixel size and detection area were 6.5 $\mu\text{m} \times$ 6.5 μm and 13 mm \times 13 mm, respectively). Spatial separation of the fluorescence X-ray signals was ensured by using two spherical mirrors (see Figure 1). The intensity readings from each pixel of the CMOS camera were converted into the absorption coefficient at individual energies. To compensate for the energy dependence of the incident X-ray intensity and the position dependence of the detection efficiency, the measured fluorescence signals were normalized by those of CaF_2 , representing I_0 . The collected O K-edge spectra were recorded in the range 525–535 eV with a time resolution of ca. 3 s per spectrum.

Electrochemical Cell Set-Up. The electrochemical part of the experiments was realized in a three-electrode PTFE single-compartment cell with a Pt auxiliary electrode and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode.²⁹ All potentials were then recalculated and are quoted in the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) scale. The PTFE cell was equipped with a Si_3N_4 window to provide a connection to the high-vacuum part of the beamline. Working electrodes composed of RuO_2 and $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ were deposited directly on the Si_3N_4 window. The RuO_2 electrode was initially prepared by Ru deposition by electron beam evaporation (E-flux, ADCAP Vacuum Technology Co., Ltd.). The thickness of the deposited Ru was 20 nm (with 10 nm of a sputtered Ti underlayer on the Si_3N_4 window before depositing Ru). The RuO_2 electrode was prepared by thermal oxidation of the deposited Ru layer at 600 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h. The thickness of the deposited layers and underlayers was optimized to achieve less than 60% attenuation of the X-rays in the electrode and interphase to enable detection of the generated fluorescence from the backside through the window.

In the case of $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$, the original nanoparticulate catalysts (particle size 10 nm) were prepared by a spray-freeze drying (SFFD) approach as described in ref 12. Final electrodes for XAS measurements were prepared by drop-casting from an ink containing Ru–Mn–O directly on the Ti-covered (10 nm) Si_3N_4 window. The Ru–Mn–O-containing ink was prepared from a water-based suspension containing 2 g of the prepared Ru–Mn–O material per liter of suspension. The necessary film stability was achieved by addition of 15 μL of a Nafion suspension (Aldrich). The suspension was freshly sonicated before the deposition of 20 μL of the ink at the Si_3N_4 window. The deposited films were X-ray-transparent at energies close to 530 eV and sufficiently homogeneous with respect to the lateral resolution of the fluorescence detector.

The deposited electrodes were contacted by an indium solder. The solder and contacting lead were insulated by a nonconductive epoxy resin. Potential control during the experiments was achieved by using an HSV-110 automatic polarization system (Hokuto Denko, Japan). All experiments were performed in 0.1 M HClO_4 (pH 1) which was deaerated prior to and during experiments. It needs to be noted that the measured voltammograms are affected by the low lateral conductivity of the thin-layer Ti contact, which hinders a direct comparison of the potentials measured for different electrodes. For that matter, the observed spectral signals are commented primarily with respect to the onset of the OER/CER processes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ruthenium Dioxide. A comparison of the electrochemical behavior of the RuO_2 electrode in acidic chloride-free solution and chloride-containing solution is given in Figure 2. Despite the similarity of the current responses of the RuO_2 electrode to

Figure 2. Cyclic voltammograms recorded on a thermally grown RuO₂ electrode in 0.1 M HClO₄ (left) and 0.1 M HClO₄ containing 0.05 M NaCl (right) at a polarization rate of 5 mV/s.

cyclic polarization in chloride-free (see Figure 2 left) and chloride-containing (see Figure 2 right) perchloric acid (pH 1), a closer examination shows a profound effect of the presence of chlorides on the electrocatalytic activity of ruthenium dioxide in anodic gas-evolving reactions. Addition of chlorides to an overall chloride concentration of 0.05 M leads to two notable changes in the observed voltammograms. In the presence of chlorides one observes a significant increase in the anodic activity of the RuO₂ electrode. This overall increase in the electrocatalytic activity is also accompanied by a decrease in the onset of the exponential current increase by about 50 mV to less positive potentials. Note that in both cases the shape of the recorded voltammograms is affected by relatively high uncompensated *iR* drop associated with low thickness of the metal contact at the Si₃N₄ window (10 nm), which, namely, in the case of chloride-free solutions, dominates the double-layer charging current, driving both branches of the voltammogram to anodic values. The contribution of the double-layer charging gets more pronounced in chloride-containing solutions, which suggests an enhanced corrosion of RuO₂ electrodes in chloride-containing media.

It needs to be noted that the recorded anodic current in the case of chloride-free solution (in the potential interval characterized by exponential current response) can be attributed to the oxygen evolution; the current response in chloride-containing solution is composed of two contributions, corresponding, in addition to the OER, also to the CER. It is also known²³ that ruthenium oxides show a high selectivity toward chlorine evolution; hence, one should expect a profound effect of the chloride presence on the in situ O K-edge spectra.

A summary of the spectro-electrochemical behavior of RuO₂ in chloride-free and chloride-containing solutions is shown in Figure 3, which presents two-dimensional contour maps reflecting the changes of XAS signal intensities recorded during cyclic polarization. The anodic behavior in chloride-free media has been reported previously and is characterized by a pronounced increase in absorption at 531 eV upon anodic polarization.²⁹

This increase in absorption integrates two main contributions—one attributable to the surface-confined OOH groups²⁷ and the other to the electrochemically evolved gaseous oxygen³² (see Figure 4a). The main increase in the population of oxygen-containing reaction intermediates, which coincides with the exponential increase of the anodic current, is accompanied by a pronounced reversible decrease of the absorption at 533 eV (see Figure 4c), which is attributed to a change in the local electronic structure (oxygen vacancies confined to Ru in *cus* sites) triggered by the start of the catalytic cycle of the oxygen evolution. The onset of the bulk oxygen evolution significantly affects the population of electronic states available to accommodate excited 1s electrons of oxygen.^{24,33} It needs to be noted that the spectral behavior of the RuO₂ does not change with cycling (see Figures S1–S4 in the Supporting Information).

In the presence of chlorides, one observes a significantly altered spectral response. In contrast to the spectra of the chloride-free solutions, the main area of the spectral response in the presence of chlorides is observed in the spectral region 532–533 eV. A detailed outline of the specific changes to O K-edge absorption in the energy range relevant to OER triggered by the presence of chlorides is given in Figure 4.

Figure 3. 2D colored surface maps showing the progression of the O K-edge spectra of the RuO₂ electrode during cyclic polarization in 0.1 M HClO₄ (left) and 0.1 M HClO₄ containing 0.05 M NaCl (right) at 5 mV/s. The map summarizes the development of the populations of oxygen-containing species at the RuO₂ surface during three consecutive cycles. The color scheme represents the absorption coefficient as a function of the electrode potential.

Figure 4. Comparison of the potential dependence of the absorption coefficient $\Delta\mu$ at 531 eV (a), 534 eV (b), 533 eV (c), and 529 eV (d) during cycling of the thermally grown RuO_2 electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 (left) and 0.1 M HClO_4 containing 0.05 M NaCl (right) at 5 mV/s. The arrows mark the direction of the polarization. The data collected in the presence of chlorides were recorded in the first three cycles. The assignment of the cycles is given in the figure legend.

It also needs to be stressed that the XAS spectra recorded in the absence of chlorides are essentially independent of the electrode history. The O K-edge spectra recorded in the same potential range in the presence of chlorides show pronounced development during electrode cycling. The most notable change with respect to the behavior recorded in the absence of chlorides is encountered at the energy of 531 eV (see Figure 4a). In the case of the experiments carried out in the absence of chlorides, the absorption coefficient at this energy reversibly increases with electrode potential to reflect an accumulation of surface-confined OOH groups^{27,29} as well electrocatalytic formation of oxygen. The same experiment carried out in chloride-containing solution shows strikingly different behavior, in which the absorbance at 531 eV on the pristine electrode initially increases with applied potential to reflect formation of oxygen as well as its intermediates at the surface. In contrast to chloride-free solutions, however, the absorbance increase changes into a plateau at potentials positive to 1.7 V vs RHE. This behavior suggests a blocking of the surface via chloride adsorption at these potentials, as the absorption coefficient at 531 eV (reflecting the population of O_2 as well as OOH) shows little sensitivity to the applied potential. Further cycling of the electrode in the whole potential range causes no change in the absorption at 531 eV (see red and blue curves in Figure 4a). This type of behavior indicates that the anodic polarization of RuO_2 in the presence of 0.05 M chlorides leads to little formation of oxygen.

Surprisingly, there is practically no difference in spectral response recorded at 529 eV in the presence and absence of chlorides (see Figure 4d). The observed behavior indicates that the formation of OH/O species at the surface is not perturbed by the presence of chloride and is not directly related to the catalytic cycle of oxygen evolution nor of chlorine evolution. Coincidentally, one observes a dramatic change in the potential-controlled absorption at 533 eV (Figure 4c). The change in absorption at 533 eV in the absence of chlorides (when the electrode exclusively evolves oxygen) is attributed to a change in the local electronic structure of the catalyst under operando conditions when the active sites of the oxygen evolution are confined to Ru in *cus* positions.²⁹ The reversible decrease of the absorption at 533 eV is proportional to the extent of the chlorine evolution. This shift in selectivity toward CER apparently reflects blocking of the Ru sites in *cus* positions which are responsible for OER in the absence of chlorides. This disturbs the electron transfer connected with the OER, resulting in a potential-controlled increase of the absorption at 533 eV in the OER/CER-relevant potential range in contrast to the absorption decrease observed in the absence of chlorides (see Figure 4c).

Aside from the absorption changes reflecting the formation of the oxygen-containing intermediates as well as of the formed oxygen, one also observes a change in the absorption in the energy range characteristic for liquid water. While in the case of the regime where the RuO_2 supports only oxygen evolution one observes a hysteretic decrease of the absorption at 534 eV

(see Figure 4b) at potentials positive to 1.7 V vs RHE, in the case of chloride-containing solutions one observes slightly different behavior when the absorption at 534 eV decreases at potential positive to 1.2 V and remains potential independent at potentials positive to 1.4 V. It needs to be stressed that the spectral change at 534 eV is fully reversible, showing no hysteresis between anodic and cathodic branches of the voltammogram. The observed behavior is compliant with a situation in which the total water content near the electrode decreases with potential. Such a situation can be ascribed either to changes in the double layer or to a formation of gases replacing water in the layer adjacent to the electrode surface. The assignment of the observed absorption decrease to potential-driven gas evolution (replacing liquid water) is, however, less likely, given the fact that the absorption decrease at 534 eV precedes the onset of the exponential current increase by ca. 0.2 V. The observed decrease in absorption might be tentatively ascribed to a change in perchlorate and chloride presence in the double layer when the content of chlorides decreases with increasing potential, in part due to chloride removal in chlorine evolution. An uptake of perchlorates replacing near the electrode chlorides consumed in the CER may result in an actual water content decrease, as the chlorides are more solvated (binding approximately 6 molecules of water per anion) while the perchlorate is comparably less solvated (averaging just 3 molecules of water per anion).³⁴ The absence of hysteresis between anodic and cathodic branches observed in the presence of chlorides can be taken as an additional confirmation of the chlorine evolution dominance. It is worth noting that, in the absence of chlorides (when oxygen evolution dominates the electrode process), one encounters a complex response of the absorption at 534 eV corresponding to water population near the electrode. The potential-triggered absorption change at this energy is rather small and difficult to rationalize.

Ru–Mn–O–Based Catalysts. While ruthenium dioxide may serve as a model catalyst selective to chlorine evolution in chloride-containing media, ruthenium-based oxides partially substituted with Mn have been reported to retain high selectivity toward oxygen evolution even in the presence of chlorides.^{12,14} Interestingly, the O K-edge absorption spectrum of the Ru–Mn–O catalysts, regardless of the actual Mn content, does not differ significantly from that reported for RuO₂³³ (see Figure 5). The O K-edge absorption spectrum is dominated by two signals located at 529.6 and 532.5 eV, respectively. These two signals are typical for excitation of the 1s electron of oxygen into bands formed by a hybridization of the antibonding O 2p orbitals with the t_{2g} and e_g 4d orbitals of Ru. In this light, the intensity of the absorption at 529.6 and 532.5 eV reflects the distribution of the vacant electronic states in the material. A minimal difference between the absorption behavior of the RuO₂ and that of the Ru–Mn–O oxides indicates that the presence of Mn has an apparently negligible effect on the electronic structure of the prepared materials, which remains controlled by ruthenium.

The preference of Ru–Mn–O surfaces towards oxygen evolution is reflected also in the O K-edge X-ray absorption spectra measured under operando conditions. In contrast to ruthenium dioxide, the overall electrocatalytic activity is not significantly affected by the presence of chlorides (see Figure 6). Regardless of the chloride presence or its concentration, the Ru–Mn–O catalysts show an exponential current increase in voltammograms when the electrode potential exceeds 1.5 V vs

Figure 5. O K-edge X-ray absorption spectra of RuO₂ (bottom) and Ru_{0.95}Mn_{0.05}O₂ (top).

Figure 6. Cyclic voltammograms recorded on spray-freeze freeze drying prepared Ru_{0.95}Mn_{0.05}O₂ electrode in 0.1 M HClO₄ containing variable content of chloride at a polarization rate of 5 mV/s. The actual chloride concentrations are marked in the figure legend.

RHE. This exponential current increase is preceded by a poorly pronounced double-layer region charging, characterized by a small current in the potential range between 1.0 and 1.5 V. It needs to be noted that the capacitive current remains rather

Figure 7. 2D colored surface map showing the progression of O K-edge spectra of $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode during cyclic polarization in 0.1 M HClO_4 containing 0.0 M (a), 0.01 M (b), 0.05 M (c), and 0.1 M NaCl (d). The polarization rate was 5 mV/s. The map summarizes the development of the populations of oxygen-containing species at the surface during three consecutive cycles. The color scheme represents the absorption coefficient as a function of the electrode potential.

low and decreases with increasing chloride concentration. The overall current response in the double-layer region remains dominated by an uncompensated iR drop due to the thin-layer nature of the current collector (10 nm of Ti). Despite the similarity of the recorded voltammograms, the Faradaic efficiency (i.e., selectivity toward oxygen evolution) decreases in the studied chloride concentration range from 100% (in pure acid) to ca. 80% (at 0.1 M concentration).¹²

This change in selectivity should also be reflected in the in situ recorded O K-edge spectra (see Figures 7–11). A comparison of the 2D maps reflecting a change in absorbance in the 525–535 eV range, however, does not show a pronounced effect of the chloride presence on the recorded spectral response (see Figure 7). The differential absorption spectra on the O K-edge are dominated by potential-driven changes of absorption at 529, 531, and 533 eV, as one should expect for oxygen evolution on Ru-based oxides.^{27,29} A detailed analysis of the change of the absorption coefficients at individual energies corresponding to OH/O (529 eV), O_2/OOH (531 eV), and local electron structure resonance (533 eV), however, outlines a slight change of the spectral behavior with respect to the RuO_2 (see Figures 8–11).

One of the notable changes is observed for the absorption of OH/O surface-confined species (Figures 8b–11b). The absorption signal located at 529 eV shows a reversible increase with increasing potential in the potential range 1.0–1.7 V vs RHE. The accumulation of these oxygen-containing species is

evident already at potentials significantly negative to the standard potential of oxygen evolution. In this light one cannot attribute this accumulation of the surface oxygen species directly to intermediates of the oxygen evolution process. It also needs to be noted that the spectral signal at 529 eV is affected neither by chloride concentration nor by electrode history. Given the fact that the selectivity of the Ru–Mn–O electrode toward oxygen evolution decreases with increasing chloride concentration, one may assume that this buildup of oxygen at the electrode surface is not directly related to the anodic gas evolution reactions.

While the 2D maps do not suggest a profound change of absorption in the region indicative of formation of gaseous oxygen or accumulation of peroxy species at the electrode surface (531 eV), a closer examination reveals a change in the recorded spectral responses of both with electrolyte concentration (see Figure 8a–11a). In the absence of chlorides the absorption signal at 531 eV increases reversibly with potential. In the anodic scan the absorption coefficient remains constant until one reaches a potential of ca. 1.4 V vs RHE, which coincides with an onset of the exponential increase of the anodic current. The absorption signal then remains practically proportional to the applied potential at all potentials above 1.5 V. A change in the polarization direction leads also to a decrease of the absorption coefficient. A potential-controlled decrease of the absorption coefficient in the cathodic scan of each cycle is evident for potentials positive to ca. 1.4 V vs RHE.

Figure 8. Potential dependence reflecting the variation of absorption coefficient change $\Delta\mu$ at 531 eV (a), 529 eV (b), and 533 eV (c) during cycling of the spray–freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 at 5 mV/s. The data were collected during the first three cycles. The assignment of the cycles is given in the figure legend.

The spectral behavior at 531 eV qualitatively changes after the addition of chlorides. In chloride-containing solutions, the absorption at 531 eV starts to increase at rather negative potentials of about 1.0 V vs RHE. This onset of absorption increase at 531 eV appears ca. 0.5 V earlier than in the absence of chlorides. It needs to be stressed that, under these conditions, the observed increase in absorption cannot be related to evolved oxygen and represents solely an accumulation of the OOH groups at the surface. Surprisingly, the absorption coefficient at 531 eV stops increasing with the applied potential at 1.4 V, when one observes an onset of the exponential current increase. While on the pristine electrode (i.e. in the first cycle) the absorption coefficient reaches a plateau, the subsequent cycles shows a clear decrease of the absorption at 531 eV. It needs to be noted that this qualitative change of the absorption behavior brings up a pronounced hysteresis between the anodic and cathodic branches (see Figures 9a–11a).

The absorption change at 531 eV (reflecting either oxygen evolution or formation and accumulation of the OOH species) is mirrored also in the absorption at 533 eV. The absorption behavior at 533 eV reflects a gradual development of the catalyst's electronic structure under operando

conditions. Regardless of the chloride concentration, the absorption coefficient at 533 eV decreases with increasing electrode potentials positive to 1.4 V vs RHE. This absorption change coincides with the onset of the exponential current increase (see Figures 8c–11c).

The behavior observed on Ru–Mn–O electrodes sheds additional light on the OER mechanism on Ru–Mn–O phases. Assuming that the oxygen evolution in principle proceeds as a sequence of four one-electron transfer steps, one can identify the rate-limiting step from the accumulation of individual intermediates of the OER at the electrode. This means that the kinetic control of the OER process by the second electron transfer should result in accumulation of the surface-confined OH. This increase in absorption of OH, however, should not be accompanied by any accumulation of surface-confined O or OOH. In a similar way, should the reaction be controlled by the third electron transfer, then the accumulation of surface-confined O (intermediate entering the third electron transfer step) should dominate the measured spectra. It needs to be noted that this absorption signal may not be accompanied by any accumulation of surface-confined OOH.

Figure 9. Potential dependence reflecting the variation of absorption coefficient change $\Delta\mu$ at 531 eV (a), 529 eV (b), and 533 eV (c) during cycling of the spray-freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 /0.01 M NaCl at 5 mV/s. The data were collected during the first three cycles. The assignment of the cycles is given in the figure legend.

The experimentally observed behavior of Ru–Mn–O records an increase in absorption at 529 eV (surface-confined OH/O). This increase starts well below the onset of the actual oxygen evolution characterized by an exponential increase of the current. This increase is reversible, and it is observed throughout the entire studied potential interval without being particularly sensitive to the onset of the oxygen evolution. At the same time, we observe a similar increase in the absorption at 531 eV which is characteristic for both surface-confined OOH and gaseous oxygen. The fact that we observe a simultaneous increase in absorption for OH/O and OOH along with zero sensitivity of the signal of the OH/O intermediate toward the actual onset of the OER current does not allow us to assign the kinetic control to the second electron.

The absorption behavior observed at 531 eV, on the other hand, shows a complex pattern significantly affected by the onset of the OER current. The absorption at 531 eV starts well ahead of the actual OER onset, indicating that OOH may be accumulated at the surface without actual relation to the OER. The onset of the oxygen evolution, on the other hand, results in a decrease of the absorption at 531 eV, which is rather counterintuitive behavior, as the absorption at 531 eV is

characteristic not only for surface-confined OOH but also for gaseous oxygen. In this light, the observed decrease in the absorption at 531 eV indicates that the formation of O_2 (which ought to boost the absorption at 531 eV) is offset by a simultaneous decrease of the surface population of the OOH intermediate. This behavior is, therefore, in qualitative agreement with the theoretical prediction for kinetic control by the third electron transfer.

A detailed analysis of the absorption at 531 eV qualifies the selectivity of the ruthenium manganese oxides in parallel with oxygen and chlorine evolution. First, one needs to stress that the accumulation of OOH in the presence and absence of chlorides follows different behavior. In the absence of chlorides, the OOH formation and/or accumulation is not observed before the onset of the exponential anodic current, and the continuous increase of the population of all conceivable intermediates of the OER with potential does not allow to pin down a single reaction step as a rate-limiting one. On the other hand, in the presence of chlorides the accumulation of OOH proceeds well before the actual onset of gas-evolving reactions. In this case, the onset of gaseous oxygen evolution is accompanied by a decrease of the OOH population at the surface. This type of behavior is consistent

Figure 10. Potential dependence reflecting the variation of absorption coefficient change $\Delta\mu$ at 531 eV (a), 529 eV (b), and 533 eV (c) during cycling of the spray-freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 /0.05 M NaCl at 5 mV/s. The data were collected during the first three cycles. The assignment of the cycles is given in the figure legend.

with a situation in which the third electron transfer becomes rate limiting. The observed behavior then suggests that the addition of chlorides streamlines the oxygen evolution process on Ru–Mn–O surfaces from multiple mechanisms which apparently apply in the absence of chlorides to a single one in which the oxygen evolution process is controlled by the third electron transfer. The recorded spectra also suggest that the oxygen-evolving process is still confined to the vicinity of the surface Ru as attests to the decrease of the available energy levels formed by a hybridization of $2p^*$ orbitals with Ru $4d e_g$ orbitals. The overall electrocatalytic activity of Ru–Mn–O catalysts is still characterized by a relatively pronounced change of the electronic structure reflecting the transfer of the electrons from water to the electrode through the catalyst. The actual effect of the present Mn—which seems to be essential in steering the selectivity of the Ru–Mn–O surfaces—cannot be elucidated from experimental spectra and would require a dedicated theoretical study.

CONCLUSIONS

The *in situ* O K-edge X-ray absorption spectra adequately reflect the difference between the states of the oxide electrode in oxygen and in parallel oxygen and chlorine evolution. In the case of RuO_2 , the oxygen evolution in the absence of chlorides

is characterized by an accumulation of surface-confined OOH (third electron transfer intermediate) and by formation of gaseous oxygen, both showing a potential-triggered increase of absorption at 531 eV. The oxygen evolution process is further characterized by a change of the local electronic structure, which shows a decrease of the absorption at 533 eV. This signal indicates the active site for the water oxidation, which seems to be confined to coordinatively unsaturated sites (*cus*) at the catalyst's surface leading to an anomalous filling of the $4d e_g$ orbitals during oxygen evolution. The presence of chlorides changes the surface behavior in such a way that the surface of RuO_2 becomes gradually selective for chlorine evolution instead of oxygen evolution. It shows itself in gradual suppression of the absorption increase at 531 eV which is otherwise typical for OER. This suppression is more pronounced in subsequent cycles, suggesting that the selective chlorine evolution requires an initial formation of the surface-confined OOH species. The shift of the selectivity toward chlorine evolution is further demonstrated by the absorption at 533 eV which, in contrast to the behavior typical for chloride-free solution, shows a potential-controlled increase in absorption.

In the case of Ru–Mn–O oxides, which retain high selectivity toward oxygen evolution even in the presence of

Figure 11. Potential dependence reflecting the variation of absorption coefficient change $\Delta\mu$ at 531 eV (a), 529 eV (b), and 533 eV (c) during cycling of the spray–freeze freeze drying prepared $\text{Ru}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{O}_2$ electrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 /0.10 M NaCl at 5 mV/s. The data were collected during the first three cycles. The assignment of the cycles is given in the figure legend.

chlorides, the O K-edge spectra clearly show that both competing processes proceed on different fractions of the catalyst's surface. In the absence of chlorides, one observes a suppression of the formation of surface OOH intermediates at potentials preceding the exponential oxygen evolution. This suggests that none of the conceived reaction steps exerts kinetic control. The oxygen evolution process is again accompanied by a decreasing absorption at 533 eV in the oxygen evolution region, confirming that the essential interaction of the OER intermediates with the catalyst's surface occurs primarily via Ru *cus* sites in a manner similar to that in RuO_2 . In the presence of chlorides, on the other hand, one observes a significant accumulation of surface-confined OOH also at potential negative to the OER onset. The population of surface-confined OOH drops rapidly once the oxygen evolution starts, indicating that the OER in the presence of chlorides is kinetically controlled by the third electron transfer.

The available spectroscopic data suggest that, in the case of the Ru-based/dominated materials, the key factor affecting the selectivity between chlorine and oxygen evolution is the ability of the catalyst to leave the surface-confined Ru *cus* sites chloride-free under the reaction conditions. Apparently, this is much easier to achieve in the case of Ru–Mn–O materials than for the RuO_2 . The experimental data indicate that

chloride absorption in fact promotes the formation of OOH sites on Ru–Mn–O phases.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

SI Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acselectrochem.5c00033>.

Differential *in situ* O K-edge spectra of continuous cycling of the RuO_2 electrode in chloride-free perchloric acid (PDF)

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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